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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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JUVENILE NASOPHARYNGEAL ANGIOFIBROMA: A CASE REPORT

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ANNOTATION

Juvenile nasopharyngeal angiofibroma (JNA) is an uncommon benign tumor that primarily affects male adolescents' nasopharynx and accounts for fewer than 1% of all head and neck neoplasms.. This aggressive tumor frequently spreads destructively locally, reaching the base of the skull and into the cranium. Clinically, however, it is unclear; the typical presenting symptom, with or without epistaxis and rhinorrhea, is painless, gradual unilateral nasal blockage. A thorough history, clinical examination, radiography, nasal endoscopy, and the use of specialized imaging methods like arteriography, computer tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging are all used to diagnose JNA. A fibrocellular stroma with spindle cells and an uneven vascular pattern are visible upon histopathological examination, along with a randomly arranged collagen arrangement. Due to their intricate anatomical placement, they are extremely vascular, benign, and locally spreading, making surgery challenging.

Key words: etiology, immunopathogenesis, juvenile angiofibroma, nasopharyngeal angiofibroma, exudative otitis media.

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ЮВЕНИЛЬНАЯ НОСОГЛОТОЧНАЯ АНГИОФИБРОМА: КЛИНИЧЕСКИЙ СЛУЧАЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ювенильная ангиофиброма носоглотки (ЮНА) — редкая доброкачественная опухоль, которая поражает преимущественно носоглотку подростков мужского пола и составляет менее 1% из всех новообразований головы и шеи. Эта агрессивная опухоль часто деструктивно распространяется локально, достигая основания черепа. *Этиология неясного* происхождения; типичным симптомом, сопровождающимся носовым кровотечением, ринореей и безболезненная односторонняя заложенность носа. Для диагностики ЮНА используются тщательный анамнез, клиническое обследование, рентгенография, назальная эндоскопия и использование специализированных методов визуализации, таких как ангиография, компьютерная томография и магнитно-резонансная томография. При гистопатологическом исследовании видна фиброцеллюлярная строма с веретенообразными клетками и неровным сосудистым рисунком, а также хаотичное расположение коллагена. Из-за сложного анатомического расположения они чрезвычайно васкуляризированы, локально распространяются, что затрудняет хирургическое вмешательство.

Ключевые слова: этиология, иммунопатогенез, ювенильная ангиофиброма, носоглоточная ангиофиброма, экссудативный средний отит.

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YUVENIL BURUN-HALQUM ANGIOFIBROMA: KLINIK HOLAT

ANNOTATSIYA

Yuvenil burun-halqum angiofibroma (YBA) kamdan-kam uchraydigan xavfsiz o'sma bo'lib, u asosan erkak o'smirlarning burun-halqumida uchraydi va barcha bosh va bo'yin o'smalarining 1% dan kamrog'ini tashkil qiladi. Bu agressiv o'simta destruktiv tarzda mahalliy tez tarqalib, bosh suyagining pastki qismigacha yetib boradi. Biroq, klinik jihatdan etiologiyasi aniq emas; burundan qon ketishi, rinoreya, og'riqsiz bir tomonlama burun bekilib qolishi tipik simptomlariga kiradi. YBA tashxisini qo'yish uchun kasallik tarixi, klinik tekshiruv, rentgenografiya, burun endoskopiyasi, arteriografiya, kompyuter tomografiyasi va magnit-rezonans tomografiya kabi maxsus ko'rik usullaridan foydalaniladi. Gistopatologik tekshiruvda fibroxujayrali stroma notekis ko'rinishda va xotik tarzda joylashgan kollagen bo'ladi. Murakkab anatomik joylashuvi tufayli ular mahalliy tarqalib, jarrohlik amaliyotini qiyinlashtiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: etiologiya, immunopatogenez, yosh angiofibroma, burun-halqum angiofibromasi, ekssudativ o'rta otit.

INTRODUCTION

A benign tumor of the nasopharynx is known as juvenile nasopharyngeal angiofibroma (JNA). It explains 0.5% of all head and neck tumors, one in every 150,000 cases. There is a clear male predominance among the affected adolescents and young adults, aged 14 to 25.[1,14]

This tumor was originally described in the fifth century B.C. by Hippocrates. Friedberg first described it as juvenile angiofibroma in 1940.[16] The label "juvenile" is disputed because JNA can also affect elderly people. However, this phrase is kept because the great majority of cases actually occur in the age range of 14 to 25. The high expression of androgen receptors (AR) in males may account for the predominance, indicating that JNA is androgen dependent.[16]

JNA is divided into three categories based on radiological and clinical characteristics. Lesions primarily confined to the nasal cavity, paranasal sinus, nasopharynx, or pterygopalatine fossa are classified as type I. Type II JNAs have an intact dura mater with an anterior and/or minor middle cranial fossa extension, reaching into the infratemporal fossa, buccal area, or orbital cavity. Type III is a large tumor lobe in the middle cerebral fossa that resembles a calabash.[17]

Uncertainty surrounds JNA's beginnings and evolution. The hamartoma and vascular malformation ideas are now under discussion.[18] Regression is reported to occur in rare circumstances, similar to hamartomas.

Fibroblasts or vascular endothelial cells are the histologic source of JNA.[19] It's also up for debate as to whether one component initiates the growth and the other passively observes it or if both proliferate and expand together. This subject is clarified in part by recent genetic and immunohistochemical investigations.

Research has been conducted to ascertain the tumor's pathophysiology through the examination of the expression levels of different growth factors and oncogenes, including C-KIT and C-MYC.[20] When compared to orbital cavernous hemangiomas, JNF exhibits significantly greater immunological staining with CD34, vascular endothelial growth factor, flt-1, and flk-1, indicating its vasoproliferative character. This provides credence to the theory that the vascular endothelial cells can be stimulated to develop into diverse mesenchymal nonhemopoietic cell phenotypes and can eventually become postembryonic undifferentiated mesenchymal cells.[18] JNA production has been linked to the GSTM 1 gene. This tumor exhibits loss of GSTM 1 (null genotype) expression.[8,20]

Given its sex selectivity and comparatively early diagnosis age, JNA appears to be hormone reliant during development. There were disparities in the outcomes of several authors' studies on estrogen receptors (ERs), progesterone receptors, and ARs in JNA. The monoclonal antibodies that exclusively identify alpha-ER and not the beta ER protein may be the cause of these differences.[9,20]

No discernible changes in blood hormone levels are seen, despite reports of hormonal abnormalities in JNA patients and the presence of AR and/or ERs in tumor tissues. Hormonal effect in JNA is still debatable.[14]

CASE REPORT

A 16-year-old male patient presented to the 1st Clinic of the Samarkand State Medical Institute's Department of Otorhinolaryngology with complaints of decreased hearing on both sides, mainly on the left side, congestion, tinnitus, autophony, and a sensation of fluid transfusion. He also complained of difficulty in nasal breathing and periodic nosebleeds.

According to his medical history, the patient has been ill for three years, and there is no noteworthy family history or past medical history associated with the disease. The first symptoms included periodic ear congestion and decreased hearing in the left ear. The patient visited a local doctor at his place of residence, who diagnosed acute otitis media and prescribed appropriate treatment. There was a short-term improvement, but after two weeks, the symptoms returned, and the hearing worsened. The doctor referred him to an ENT doctor for further examination. After the examination, an audiological examination was recommended, and a diagnosis of exudative otitis media was made based on the results. Appropriate treatment and observation were prescribed. After two months of treatment, the patient began to notice a decrease in hearing in the right ear and difficulty in nasal breathing. The patient complained specifically of mouth breathing during sleep, although there was no clinical pallor. Eight months after the appearance of the first symptoms,

nosebleeds appeared, and the patient was sent for consultation to the 1st Clinic of the Samarkand State Medical Institute.

From his life history, he is susceptible to colds, and he was not treated in the hospital. He denies allergies to food or medications. There was no tenderness on palpation and no external facial deformity. From his life history, he is susceptible to colds. He was not treated in hospital. Denies allergies to food or medications. There was no tenderness on palpation and no external facial deformity.

Upon examination, the external auditory canals were found to be clear. The patient's right eardrum appeared dull gray in color with changes in its mobility, while the left eardrum was sharply retracted with the handle of the malleus protruding and an absence of the light cone. A specific otoscopic sign of a "spoked wheel," (picture 1) which is characteristic of the presence of effusion in the middle ear, was also identified. This sign is defined as a dull gray appearance of the tympanic membrane with swollen vasculature arranged like the spokes of a bicycle wheel, covering 50% or more of the inferior tympanic membrane.

The nasal passages were filled with mucus, and after cleaning, a bluish-colored, smooth-surfaced obstruction was observed in the posterior sections of the left half of the nose. Fiber endoscopy revealed an asymmetric, red-bluish formation in the nasopharynx on the left side with a finely tuberos surface that covered the left choana completely and partially blocked the right half. During digital examination of the nasopharynx, a dense, immobile tuberos formation was palpated. The patient reported difficulty breathing through the nose, with complete obstruction of the left half.

There was no tenderness upon palpation, and no external facial deformities were observed. The patient had a history of susceptibility to colds but denied any allergies to food or medications. He had not been treated in a hospital before.

Picture 1. Otomicroscopic picture of exudative otitis media in juvenile angiofibroma of the nasopharynx

The audiological examination revealed reduced hearing in both ears, with AS presenting conductive hearing loss of the second degree and hearing loss at speech frequencies of 52 dB, and AD presenting conductive hearing loss of the first degree and hearing loss of 32 dB. Tympanometry results showed type "B" on the left and type "C" on the right.

Based on the abnormalities found in the nasopharynx, the patient was referred for MSCT. The computed tomography revealed a tumor in the nasopharynx that had invaded into the nasal cavity (Picture 2).

The patient underwent surgical treatment, and there was minimal intraoperative bleeding during the excision. The gross specimen that was removed had a consistency that ranged from soft to firm, and it appeared white to yellow in color with areas of darker vascularity. There was no evidence of encapsulation.

Picture 3 Microslide of juvenile angiofibroma (hematoxylin-eosin staining, magnification x100)

DISCUSSION

Angiofibroma is a relatively rare tumor. There are very few documented examples involving females.[2,5,10,11] JNAs are related to sex and age. With a median age of 15, it primarily affects male teenagers, which raises questions regarding the potential involvement of sexual hormones in the disease's etiology.[9] They primarily begin in the posterolateral wall of the nasopharynx, more precisely where the roof of the pterygoid process, the vomer's horizontal process, and the palatine bone's sphenoidal process converge.[1] Patients typically exhibit nasal blockage, repeated epistaxis, and, in rare cases, facial edema when they first arrive at a late stage of the disease. Prolonged tumor growth can result in facial enlargement, proptosis, diplopia with speech difficulties, and conductive hearing loss.[9] The patient in this instance was also male. The patient in this instance was a guy, seventeen years of age, who likewise had the usual triad of discharge, stuffiness in the nose, and recurrent epistaxis in addition to right facial edema.

The sphenopalatine foramen is involved, the base of the pterygoid plate is eroding, and there is secondary involvement of the nasopharynx, among other consistent findings reported in the medical literature, despite the ongoing controversy about the origin.[2]

Magnetic resonance angiography, CT, and MRI can all be used to diagnose angiofibroma.[1] Because CT is helpful in demonstrating the loss of bony structures and the enlargement of foramen and fissures at the base of the skull, it is the most significant preoperative test.[1] One distinctive finding of JNA is the anterior bowing of the maxillary wall as a result of the presence of a mass in the pterygomaxillary space on axial CT slices, which is known as the Holman-Miller sign.[9] Furthermore, CT is used to stage tumors. To demonstrate whether a tumor has spread intracranially, MRI is helpful. MRI is also useful in differentiating between secretion retention, blockage, and sinus invasion.[1] JNA shows up on MRI as a heterogeneous mass with signal voids that match the tumor's high vascularity.[1] By identifying the feeding vessels, selective angiography enables preoperative embolization for vascular management. It displays the size and location of the feeding vessel in addition to the lesion's size and location.[1,13] The external carotid branch of the maxillary artery is

the site of vascularization most often, with background vascularization originating from blood vessels in the internal carotid artery and ascending pharyngeal artery.[4]

Preoperative embolization combined with surgery is the primary course of treatment.[4] Additional therapeutic approaches that have been used include cryotherapy, radiation, hormone therapy, artery ligation, and the application of sclerosing agents.[2,4] Future JNA treatment options might include intra-arterial immunotherapy and the application of certain angiogenesis-inhibiting drugs.[2]

CONCLUSION

JNA is a rare, highly vascular, locally invasive, unencapsulated tumor that primarily originates in the teenage male's nasopharynx. It manifests as a unilateral, painless, benign nasal obstruction, either with or without rhinorrhea and epistaxis. Clinical examination, radiography, nasal endoscopy, and specialized imaging methods like CT and MRI are used to make the diagnosis. Prognosis and treatment planning are aided by the comparatively simple classification and clinical stage processes.

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